

Representation of Inclusion in Learners' Workbooks for Grades 1 to 3 in the Kenyan Competence Based Curriculum

Samuel Kochomay

Introduction

The roots of the contemporary discourse on inclusion as social justice intervention can be traced to the American civil rights movement (Cassimere, 2018; Wolbrecht and Hero, 2005). The diffusion of inclusion principles into mainstream national values was born out of advocacy efforts by democratic movements and multinational corporations. Today, many nations have, at least in principle, declared diversity, equity and inclusion as parts of their legal and governance instruments making these principles an important part of their national value system. Kenya, in particular, has institutionalized diversity, equity and inclusion by embedding these principles in the constitution (Articles 10, 97, 100 and 232) and setting up watchdog institutions such as the National Cohesion and Integration Commission (NCIC), the National Gender and Equality Commission (NGEC) and the Kenya National Commission on Human Rights (KNCHR) to check on the fidelity in the observance and implementation of the laws and provisions on diversity, equity and inclusion in the government (Government of Kenya, 2010). To assure that the nation now and in the future lives by these principles, they (i.e. the principles) have been cascaded into the national goals of education (Numbers five, six and seven) set to promote social equity, respect for Kenya's cultural diversity and to foster positive attitudes towards other nations.

Although Kenya's Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) responds to the Constitution of Kenya 2010's intent, its rushed implementation overlooked some of the seemingly small yet very consequential fine points in the delivery of diversity, equity and inclusive education. Among the unattended fine points is whether the content in the learners' workbooks is relevant and adequate to produce diversity-aware, equity-sensitive and inclusive-responsive citizens as anticipated in the Kenyan constitution.

Studies on the implementation of CBC since its roll out in 2019 have documented a myriad of challenges. Prominent among these challenges are that the implementation found teachers ill-prepared and overworked (Akala, 2021; Mwang'ombe, 2021; Owala, 2021), that there were inadequate teaching and learning resources (Owala, 2021; Mwang'ombe, 2021), that there were content errors in the teaching materials (Mwang'ombe, 2021; Ondimu, 2018), and that parents were uninformed and unsupportive, often a result of poverty (Mwang'ombe, 2021; Owala, 2021). Apart from the findings on content errors associated with hasty implementation, there are no known studies that have paid attention to representation of inclusion in the learners' workbooks in Kenya's CBC. In an attempt

to fill this gap, this study examines representation of inclusion in the images in learners' workbooks for Grades 1-3 of the Kenyan competence based curriculum.

The study adopts a media representations approach. The concept of media representation suggests that any media text (images, pictures, words in sound or writing, illustrations) is a representation of a constructed reality with the goal to have the audience (reader, viewer, listener) adopt such reality. Empirical studies have revealed that content in textbooks transmits cultural values and ideology (Baleghizadeh and Shayesteh, 2020), reinforces traditional values (Moreno-Fernández, Moreno-Crespo, Pedrero-García, and Hunt-Gómez, 2019), and influences learners' attitudes towards themselves, others and the society (Ndura, 2004). Furthermore, textbooks are invisible inequality-reinforcing mechanisms (Moreno-Fernandez et al., 2019), and distort reality (Moreno-Fernandez et al., 2019). This is a key assumption in this study; that the images and the written text in the learners' workbooks were deliberately chosen to advance certain meaning to achieve intended cognitive, affective or behavioural effects.

Conceptualizing inclusion

Inclusion

Inclusion cannot be understood without two other concepts; diversity and equity. Diversity refers to the range of human differences in terms of, among other things, social identities (e.g. gender), income, physical ability (e.g. people with disabilities), education and training background, personalities and values (Homan, Gündemir, Buengeler, and Van, 2020; Jones, Carter, Davis, and Wang, 2023). These differences may produce perceptual differentiations among people and such perceptions may evoke responses in others that may advantage or disadvantage the individual in question (Lumby and Coleman, 2007). Diversity can be an asset where inclusion is institutionalized or a liability in a closed system that disadvantages minorities.

Equity is a social justice principle together with access, diversity, participation and human rights (Coleman and Glover, 2010; Khechen, 2013). Equity is based on the assumption that individuals do not start at the same point in life because of social, economic or political barriers, and therefore some equity interventions must be applied to enable those left behind to catch up. While equity interventions may be inclined to proportionate share (fair and just), inclusion is the intentional effort to ensure that all diverse individuals are valued and feel valued, involved and respected. Communities, companies and institutions that have embraced inclusion have reported positive contributions such as enhanced diverse participation in the community, organization and society (Ferdman, 2014).

In this study, inclusion is seen as a reflection of the diversity depicted in the images analysed, and equity is analysed as the proportional representation of the diversity in the same images relative to the population. Portrayal of diversities has been used as a proxy

for inclusion intervention by the authors of the workbooks. In other words, the study looks at how authors deploy depiction of diversity as an indirect indicator for inclusion in the images in workbooks.

Representation biases in textbooks

Representation biases refer to distorted, prejudiced, discriminatory and unfair characterization of a situation, an idea, a group, or a person. These biases are either positive or negative. Representation biases are present across print media (newspapers, magazines and books) and electronic media (radio and television) and have been studied for a long time. Broadly, studies have revealed that representation biases reinforce cultural hegemonies, perpetuate stereotypes, promote discrimination, induce change and also result in disinhibitions towards injustices against the negatively stereotyped groups (AlDahou, Ibrahim, Park, Rahwan, and Zaki, 2024; Harris and Sanborn, 2014).

Exposure to inclusive content is the antidote to representational biases. A recent experiment by AlDahou and colleagues found that exposure to inclusive content have significant effect in reducing biases in the perceptions of minorities but equally confirmed that non-inclusive content can reinforce and amplify the biases and thus may exacerbate existing stereotypes, attitudes and inequalities (AlDahou, Ibrahim, Park, Rahwan, and Zaki, 2024).

One persistent, unyielding and resilient representation bias in school textbooks is gender bias which has been found to produce an ‘oppressive world’ (Cameron, 1990, p.13) and which has ‘deleterious effects’ to female learners that include feelings and perceptions of alienation, devaluation, lowered expectations and exclusion. (Lesikin, 2001, p.281). At the individual level, it is likely to result in low self-esteem, frustrations and also restricts individuals’ roles by setting expectations and boundaries of what they can and cannot do in family and community life and in society at large, consequently limiting their potential (Mirza, 2004). Such representational biases provide negative models for children and are likely to undermine their participation, harmony and justice within and in their communities.

Whereas other actors may have influence on what goes into the school textbooks’ content (text and images), Gharbavi and Mousavi (2012) maintain that it is primarily the author’s opinions and their attitudes that decide what is printed in the textbook. Although textbooks and workbooks are broadly guided by education policy and curriculum, the author has the freedom of choosing how to present the text and images to meet the broadly defined content in the curriculum.

This study was conducted in a Kenyan context where inclusion is an institutionalized national aspiration with watchdog institutions to monitor fidelity in the observance of laws governing diversity, equity and inclusion, with national education goals which seek to promote social equity, respect cultural diversity and foster positive attitudes towards other

nations. The objects of representation selected for analysis constitute important identities (gender, age groups, roles, social classes, religious, ethnic groups, racial identities and people living with disability) that are central to Kenya's social justice aspirations. The Kenyan law sets representation quotas for ethnic groups and regions in public service as well as gender and minorities (ethnic, racial, people with disabilities) in both national parliaments and county assemblies. If inclusion is so explicitly articulated in the constitution and other governance instruments, the education content should also take a cue and prepare learners in the understanding of the normative practices in their society.

Previous research

Inclusive content and Kenya's CBC

Kenya's CBC was a shift in response to constitutional prescriptions, and fast-paced globalization that called for more inclusive education in line with local and global development agendas such as SDG 4. Although advocacy towards inclusion in education has a long history, more intensified efforts for mainstreaming inclusion in the learners' content have become more apparent in the last decades (Tikly, 2019; Nordin and Sundberg, 2018). Rolled out in the new constitutional era, Kenya's CBC offered a better promise for more inclusive education and inclusive content (Gichuru, et al., 2021).

Even with the consensus that CBC is better in meeting the needs of all learners as regards inclusive education, fierce criticism has been directed at the long term cost and its hasty implementation. The prominent challenges to Kenya's CBC can be disaggregated into challenges related to teachers, learning resources, content, and the parental role in learning. Research reveals that the rollout found teachers ill-prepared, that teaching and learning materials were inadequate, that teachers were overworked, that publishers of learning materials overlooked content errors and that parents were uninformed, unsupportive, and incapable of shouldering cost demands for the CBC practical lessons (Akala, 2021; Mwang'ombe, 2021; Ondimu, 2018; Owala, 2021).

These studies flagged content errors as one of the consequences of the hasty implementation. This implies that inadequate attention was paid to the content of learning materials for educating learners on matters considered important in the national development agenda. The content as implied in the national goals of education includes content intended to prepare learners towards being more responsive to diversity, equity and inclusion. Given the Kenya's aspiration of preparing learners to be more cosmopolitan and globally-versatile citizens who are responsive to diversity needs, the question is: how inclusive is the content in the learners' workbooks for facilitating inclusion consciousness?

The Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) is the agency responsible for approving the publishing of workbooks (pupil's/learner's books) and textbooks by different publishers. Private schools can choose from a range of approved workbooks. For

public schools, the government commissions publishers to print and distribute workbooks to learners across the nation. Public schools thus have to make do with what the government supplies.

Media representations theory

Media representation refers to the construction of reality of any text in any medium (Tuchman, 1978). Media in this study is used to refer to mass media such as print (books, newspaper, magazines) and electronic (radio, television). In the context of media representations, text refer to images, pictures, words in sound and writing, and illustrations. Professionals across sectors such as communication, diplomacy, business, politics, government and health employ representation devices to frame products, ideas, issues and solutions to direct and guide the direction of public opinion on a topic, a proposition or an issue (Mungwari, 2017). Since representations can be used to refer to real or fictional objects (Briggs and Cobley, 2002; Hall, 2003, p.3), media texts are constructed realities intended for the audience to believe.

Framing Theory, founded by Goffman in 1974, remains one of the most applied theories in media representations studies. Framing is an intentional act to select a particular aspect of perceived reality, make that aspect of perceived reality 'more salient in a communicating text in a way that achieves four purposes: (1) promotes a particular problem definition, (2) causal interpretation, (3) moral evaluation, and/or (4) treatment recommendation' (Entman, 1993, p.52). In framing, choices are made about what to ignore, exclude, downplay, or exaggerate by use of one or a combination of tone, layout, visual or quotes (Linström and Marais, 2012). These framing actions mirror Torres Santome's reality distortion mechanisms commonly used in textbooks (Moreno-Fernandez et al., 2019).

From the assumptions of Framing Theory, the author's choices about the images (visuals) in the analysed workbooks are deliberate rather than accidental, and choices are informed by, and are anticipated to achieve, explicit learning goals. It therefore follows that the actors (government, authors and editors) in the workbooks production chain are intentional in how and how not to depict inclusion in the choices they make on the depicting of diversities. Disproportionate representation of diversities in the images is thus seen as an intentional act aimed at advancing, reinforcing (exaggerating) or extinguishing (ignoring/downplaying) particular beliefs and attitudes. For gender, for instance, gender codes can be seen as framed and transmitted through images in workbooks. However, since images are ideological devices, they may give imprecise and inaccurate representations (Machin, 2013).

Media representation studies have mapped significant influence of representations on attitudes, perceptions and responses to the objects of representations (Giles, 2003; Harris and Sanborn, 2014). These studies reveal that negative portrayals of minorities (ethnic, racial, disability, religious) frame them as a threat taking away the dominant group's place,

status and contaminates their ideals (Tukachinsky, 2017; Ramasubramanian, Riewestahl, and Ramirez, 2023).

Representations in school textbooks

Educational content (images and text) in textbooks has significant impact on both learning and learner experiences. Textbooks are instruments of transmission of cultural values and ideology (Baleghizadeh and Shayesteh, 2020) which can be weaponized as tools of subjugation, discrimination or as instruments of empowerment. Whereas images in textbooks are excellent in aiding learning through attracting and keeping attention, they also reinforce values and cultural ideals. As Moreno-Fernandez et al. (2019) put it, 'images are not neutral... they reinforce traditional values' (p.71).

By reinforcing traditional values, textbooks become instruments of subjugation implying that for the outsiders to belong, they should lose their identities and assimilate into the mainstream. In spite of decades of advocacy towards inclusion in education, textbooks continue to transmit ideological and non-representative cultural content (Gomez-Carrasco and Gallego-Herrera, 2016). Because textbooks have influence on learners' attitudes, textbooks may alter or reinforce learners' self-perception, their perceptions of others and their perception of wider society (Ndura, 2004). This, therefore, places great responsibility on the authors and government authorities in the school textbooks content production value chain.

When badly managed, textbooks can become reality distorting mechanisms that reinforce inequalities when they cast minorities in stereotypical roles. Torres Santome identified five reality distortion mechanisms commonly seen in textbooks: suppressions (omissions), deformations (re-ordering), additions (inventions), diverted attention (framing) and blaming the subjects for its complexity (Moreno-Fernandez et al., 2019). One intervention against these distortion mechanisms is for the textbook authors to make deliberate efforts to sufficiently reflect the social changes and portray real, non-stereotypical models (Moreno-Fernández et al., 2019).

In the context of multiracial, multi-ethnic, multi-religious and multi-cultural diversities within nations, further exacerbated by globalization, the need to educate for diversity is a must, even for inward-looking, closed and extremely nationalistic societies. This is because, whether we like it or not, societies have become more diverse, and the success of such societies within and outside will depend on the diversity competence of its citizens and whether that they are capable of successfully operating socially in the global sphere. This has therefore required that educating for diversity should be an investment project for preparing learners for requisite attitudes that afford them knowledge and skills to effectively navigate a more culturally diverse world.

Empirical studies on cultural diversity in textbooks reveal that some textbooks have inclusive content depicting diversities while others ignore existing diversity reality and

depict dominant, nationalistic cultural practices and values. In their analysis of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) textbooks in Hungary, Weninger and Kiss (2013) established that two books (*Steps and Bloggers*) depicted nationalities, festivals, voices and characters from across the world. The writers of these textbooks were aware and responsive to diversity and internationalization. Examining culture-specific expressions in the English language textbooks (ELT) for Grades 6-8 in Turkey, Cakir (2010), found that the majority of teaching activities did not sufficiently integrate Turkish cultural elements but favoured the English culture. Similar study by Hamiloğlu and Mendi (2010) on cultural content in ELT in Turkey found that out of the five textbooks studied, one book almost exclusively depicted American and English cultural topics while four were more inclusive, embedding elements of various cultures. A study by Tajeddin and Teimournezhad (2015), set in Iran, found that the majority of the cultural elements in local textbooks used in language centres in Iran did not depict a specific culture, and only a small number depicted the target language culture.

These studies show that there seem to be two sets of textbook writers. One set acknowledges the reality of diversity and responds by promoting inclusion through portrayal of a more cosmopolitan and inclusive view of the world. The other set is made up of writers who take on a narrow, ethnocentric and more inward-looking nationalistic and ethnocentric view of the world. They in turn respond to their fears of a diverse world by populating school textbooks with portrayals of their perceived nationalist and cultural topics to sustain their ideological and cultural hegemony aspirations in exclusion of minorities.

Methods

This study is descriptive in its approach. Quantitative content analysis was used in studying representation of inclusion in Kenya's CBC learners' workbooks for Grades 1-3.

Sample

From seven of the seventeen workbooks approved by the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) from the Kenya Literature Bureau (KLB), a sample of 779 images were drawn through a two-stage process. An 'image' in this study refers to a photograph or artwork with human character(s) cast in a setting (frame), and such an 'image' may host a number of human characters. The choice of KLB was informed by a long publishing history going back to Kenya's pre-independence era. It is a government-owned publisher and is among the largest school textbook publishers in Kenya. Being government owned implies that the national ideological and development agenda should be revealed through their publications. It also serves Uganda, Rwanda and South Sudan.

The first stage involved selecting workbooks that: (a) had at least four learning sessions a week, (b) had a minimum of 25 images with human characters, and (c) were not

exclusively committed to religious teaching. Christian Religious Education (CRE), Islamic Religious Education (IRE) and Hindu Religious Education (HRE) were excluded on the assumption that they were likely to disproportionately depict images biased in favour of the respective religion. Out of the seventeen, seven workbooks met the criteria and were selected. Of the seven workbooks selected, two were in Kiswahili and five were in English language. Kiswahili is the second official language in Kenya and popularly spoken in at least five East African Community States.

In the second stage, the images that (a) were in colour, (b) were relatively clear (visible facial features), (c) depicted the gender of the characters, and (d) had relatively normal human features were selected. Images with exaggerated human features (cartoon-like) were excluded. Table 1 shows images per workbook.

Table 1: Sampled workbooks and images

Subject	Learning Level		
	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
English Language Activities	203	-	-
Environmental Activities	-	-	96
Hygiene and Nutrition Activities	87	77	-
Mazoezi ya Kiswahili	-	160	126
Mathematical Activities	-	30	-
Total	290	267	222

Measures and coding procedure

Instrumentation: An image in this study was defined as a photograph or artwork containing one or more human characters cast in a setting (physical) with or without written text reference. The unit of analysis was an image with human character(s) and the supplementing written text reference where available. A coding protocol and a code sheet was used to obtain data, from the 779 images, on the workbook’s characteristics (subject and the learning level), physical setting (rural or urban), gender, age groups, roles (social or occupational) of the adults in the images, social classes, religious, ethnic groups, racial identities and people with disability.

Coding procedure: Each image was coded from item 1 to 31. For each workbook, the coders began from the front, cover page to the back page. This was done for all the sampled images in all seven workbooks.

Inter-rater reliability test: Two raters were trained before coding the images. From the coded images, an inter-rater reliability test was performed on a subsample of 49 yielding acceptable inter-rater agreement (Cohen’s Kappa 0.91) considered an almost perfect agreement (Riffe, Lacy, and Fico, 2014).

Results

Characteristics of the workbooks

Of the 779 sampled images, the English Activities workbook for Grade 1 had the highest number of images (n=203; 26.1%) while Mathematical Activities workbook for Grade 2 had the least number of images (n=30; 3.9%) (see Table 2). Overall, workbooks for language subjects (English and Kiswahili activities) had more images relative to the other subjects. For image samples per level (Table 2), Grade 1 had the highest number of images (n=290; 37.2%) while Grade 3 had the least number of images (n=222; 28.5%).

Table 2: Characteristics of the workbooks

Workbook Subjects (N=779)		Learners Level (N=779)	
G1 Hygiene and Nutrition Activities	11.2% (87)	Grade 1	37.2% (290)
G1 English Activities	26.1% (203)	Grade 2	34.3% (267)
G2 Mazoezi ya Kiswahili	20.5% (160)	Grade 3	28.5% (222)
G2 Mathematical Activities	3.9% (30)		
G2 Hygiene and nutrition activities	9.9% (77)		
G3 Mazoezi ya Kiswahili	16.2% (126)		
G3 Environmental Activities	12.3% (96)		

* G1 stands for Grade 1

Representation of social classes and physical setting

In Taable 3, the middle class was disproportionately represented occurring in 91.9% (n=716) and lower class occurring 7.1% (n=55) with upper class portrayed 0.3% (n=4). The finding on middle class is consistent with how the other media have often portrayed middle class. Novels, television dramas and newspapers depict middle class characters and direct their attention towards middle class interests (Giles, 2003; Harris and Sanborn, 2014). Since these findings do not reflect proportionate representation of the social classes in Kenya, they lead to similar conclusions of media representations of social classes in other societies (Harris and Sanborn, 2014).

Table 3: Social class and physical setting

Social class (N=779)		Physical Setting (N=779)	
Upper class	0.4% (3)	Rural	46.6% (363)
Middle class	91.9% (716)	Urban	18.5% (144)
Lower class	7.1% (55)	No signifier	34.9% (272)
Not identifiable	0.6% (5)		

On depiction of the physical context (rural or urban) within which the human characters were cast, 46.6% (n=363) and 18.5 % (n=144) of the images were cast in rural and urban areas respectively. More than a third (34.9 %; n=422) of the images had no signifiers for either urban or rural settings. Using images with signifiers shows that the portrayals reasonably well reflect Kenya's population distribution in the 2019 Kenya Population and Housing Census report (KPHC) which showed that 72.9% of Kenyans reside and work in the rural areas (KNBS, 2019).

Gender, ethnic, racial, religious and age groups

Gender: Of the 2619 human characters in the images, 54.2 % (n=1420) were male while 45.8% (n=1199) were female (see Table 4). This finding gives disproportionately more presence to males than there actually are in Kenya’s population whose gender proportions are 49.5% to 50.5% for males and females respectively (KNBS, 2019).

Ethnic identities: Kenya has more than 42 state recognized ethnic groups with the largest groups being the Kikuyu, Luhya, Kalenjin, Luo and Akamba while El Molo, Makonde, Teso, Njemps, and Kuria are among some of the smallest of ethnic groups in Kenya. In Table 4, there were 19 (0.7%) depictions of Kenya’s ethnic groups which is a disproportionate absence of portrayals of Kenya’s ethnic groups in the workbooks. From over 42 ethnic groups, only Kikuyu (n=10; 0.4%), Akamba (n=5; 0.2%), Maa (n=2; 0.1%), Kalenjin(n=1) and the Luhya(n=1) had portrayals.

Racial identities: The exposure to and encounter with people who are of different racial extraction is the beginning of socialization to global diversity. Kenya’s national goals of education are intentional about preparing citizens to not only appreciate the reality of diversity across cultures, across communities but to be effective global citizens. This is important because encountering people who are racially and culturally different is a frequent and an ongoing experience. Racial identities thus mirror global diversity and confirm globalization reality. From Table 4, 97.5% (n=2553) were depictions of people of African race, 1.3% (n=35) of Asian and 0.1% (n=2) of white race.

Table 4: Gender, ethnic, racial, religious and age groups

		<i>N=2619</i>			<i>N=2619</i>
Gender	Males	54.2% (1420)	Age Groups	Children	60.6% (1586)
	Females	45.8% (1199)		Teens	5% (130)
				Early adults	29.7% (778)
Ethnic Groups	Kikuyu	0.4% (10)		Middle age	2.9% (76)
	Akamba	0.2 % (5)		Old age	0.9% (24)
	Maa	0.1% (2)		Unclassified	1.0% (25)
	Kalenjin	0.0% (1)			
	Luhya	0.0% (1)	Religion	Islam	48.9% (22)
		Christian		35.6% (16)	
		Hinduism		15.6% (7)	
Racial Groups	African	97.5% (2553)			
	White	0.1% (2)			
	Asian	1.3% (35)			

**Other religious affiliations were not portrayed*

Age groups: The age groups were classified into children (ages 0-12 years), teens (ages 13-17 years), early adults (ages 18-39), middle adults (ages 40-59) and older adults (ages 60 and above). From Table 4 above, 60.6% (n=1586) depicted children, 29.7% (n=778) early adults, 5.0% (n=130) teens, 2.9% (n=76) middle adults and 0.9% (n=24) in older adults.

Although these findings do not represent the Kenyan population proportions, it reveals the authors' contextualization of the content to match the frequent daily experiences of learners as a means to enable them to concretize learning. Children's frequency of contact with the various age groups is constrained by the school setup, which affords them more frequent contact with other children than with other age groups in the larger part of the day. Depiction of children and early adults make up 90% of all the depictions of the age groups. This may account for the fact that the author may have been deliberate in creating content that is relatable to learners by providing images they can identify with.

Religious identities: Cumulatively, 1.7 % (n=45) of the 2619 human characters depicted religious affiliations with Islam occurring 0.8 % (n=22), Christianity occurring 0.6 % (n=16) and Hinduism 0.3 % (n=2). Computing proportions within the depictions show that 48.9%, 35.6%, 15.6% were depictions for Islamic, Christian and Hindi religious affiliations respectively. These portrayals are a misrepresentation of religious affiliations in Kenya. In the 2019 KPHC report, 97.5% (46,377,370) of Kenyans were religious in the following proportions: Christians (84.9%), Islam (10.8%), Hindu (0.1%), traditionalists (0.1) and other religions (0.7%) (KNBS, 2019).

From the depictions, Islam, which was a distant second at 10.8% against Christianity which was 84.9% in the Kenya's religious proportions, had more presence in the portrayals. The reason behind this disproportionate representation may either be related to religious artefacts or a deliberate act of reality distortion by the authors and other content influencing actors in the textbook production chain. In the majority of Christian denominations, clerics and other orderlies wear religious attire and other religious paraphernalia only in and during religious occasions, rituals and events. However, the adherents do not have a prescribed religious dress. Islamic faith on the other hand has prescribed dress for women and optional dress for men both of which have religious significance. This makes Muslim faithful conspicuous in the community.

Occupations and relationships

Two sets of roles for the adults cast in the image: occupational roles (e.g. teacher) and relational roles in the family (e.g. father) were analysed. From the occupational roles (n=137) and relational roles (n=110) depicted, teacher (n=68; 49.6%) was the most popularly portrayed occupational role while mother was the most popularly portrayed relational role (n=59; 53.6%) (Table 5). The female teacher is the most depicted (n=47; 69.1%) against the male teacher (n=21; 30.9%). Although there were more female teachers (69.1 %) than male teachers (30.9%), the difference in reality in Kenya is not as wide as the portrayals reflect. However, in the experience of learners, most teachers at these learning levels are often female with whom they have intense daily contact at school before they return home to be with their mothers or other female caregivers. It is safe thus to say that for concrete learning, the authors' contextualization is not just relevant but appropriate.

Table 5: Occupational and relational roles

Occupational roles (N=137)			Relational roles (N=110)		
		Male	Female		
Teacher	68 (49.6%)	21 (30.9%)	47 (69.1%)	Father	43 (39.1%)
Farmer	23 (16.8%)	18 (78.3%)	5 (21.7%)	Mother	59 (53.6%)
Traders	10 (7.3%)	5 (50%)	5 (50%)	Grandfather	5 (4.5%)
Medical doctor	10 (7.3%)	10 (100%)	(0%)	Grandmother	3 (2.7%)
Chief	4 (2.9%)	2 (50%)	2 (50%)		
Police	4 (2.9%)	1 (25%)	3 (75%)		
Chef	3 (2.2%)	3 (100%)	(0%)		
Mason	3 (2.2%)	3 (100%)	(0%)		
Dentist	2 (1.5%)	2 (100%)	(0%)		
Vet	2 (1.5%)	2 (100%)	(0%)		
Pilot	2 (1.5%)	1 (50%)	1 (50%)		
Others	6 (4.2%)	(0%)	1 (100%)		

Notes: Others refer to roles with $\leq 1\%$ occurrence: nurse, judge, car mechanic, musician, journalist, athlete

Table 5 provides insight into the lingering traditional gender dominated occupations as well as pointing towards changes in society. Occupations that have been traditionally dominated by men such as medical doctor, vet, mason, dentist, and car mechanic have been depicted as male only occupations. Some of the occupational roles that have been popularly men’s (e.g. judge) had depictions of women. Occupations such as police officer and pilot had more portrayals of women than men.

Representation of people with disabilities

The data reveals underrepresentation and misrepresentation of people with disabilities. Of the 2619 human characters, there were 9 (0.3%) portrayals with the only type of disability depicted being physical disability. According the 2019 KPHC report, 2.2 % (0.9 million) Kenyans had some disability at the time. Whereas these authors made some effort to introduce learners to the existence of disability in the community, their weak point was presenting only one type of physical disability.

Discussion and conclusions

Discussion

This study has echoed findings in previous research that the content of textbooks reinforces traditional values, alters learners’ perceptions and may distort reality. The findings on occupational roles reveal the lingering traditional gender/occupation stereotyping but also point towards the writers’ awareness of change in society, reflecting such change in the workbooks. Occupations that have remained traditionally male such as medical doctor, vet, mason, dentist, farmer, and car mechanic on one hand and those that have been dominantly female, such as nurse and teacher, remain unchallenged in representations in the workbooks. However, the authors of these workbooks have depicted women in traditionally male occupations such as chief, pilot, police, judge and journalist. Women have made entry into occupational roles that have been popularly male (e.g. judge) and dominated others (such as police), and at par with men in roles such as trader and pilot.

The teacher has remained the most visible, dominant and prominent female occupation across the world since the 1980s (Banda, 2014; Hellinger, 1980; Kolbe and La Voie, 1981; Ullah and Skelton, 2013; Zeenatunissa, 1989). While some findings reinforce representational biases, there is an effort by the authors of textbooks to reflect contemporary reality and this points towards their consciousness about contemporary inclusion practices.

The study also points toward perception-altering distortions in the workbooks and their potential impact on learners' perceptions. Findings on portrayal of ethnic groups, gender and religious affiliations offer prominence to some groups by taking away its equitable space and awarding it to the other. Representations of ethnic and religious identities were exaggerated. One ethnic group whose proportion in the national population was 17.3% took up 52.6% of the depictions entrenching ethnic hegemony. On representation of religious affiliations, the authors flipped the weights; the most populous religious group was represented as a minority and vice versa. Further, there are many types of disabilities in the community, yet the authors depicted just one, physical disability. From Torres Santome's reality-distorting mechanisms used by textbook writers, the prominently applied mechanisms by the writers of the studied workbooks were suppression (omissions), deformations (re-ordering), and additions (inventions) (Moreno-Fernandez et al, 2019).

The findings on the portrayal of religions, ethnic and racial groups, which were proxies for inclusion, demonstrated depiction of inclusion. Though not equitable, most areas of diversity in this study were portrayed. However, ethnic minorities and the marginalized were cast in stereotypical roles. A case in point was an image of a Maasai male who was portrayed dressed in native attire in the field looking after goats. This representation concurs with Moreno-Fernández, et al (2019), i.e. that textbooks promote stereotypical images of minorities and that these images reinforce traditional values and stereotypes. Scholars concur that stereotypical representation of minorities is not often done in good faith, and even if it is done in good faith, opportunists can take advantage of such representations to marginalize and dominate minorities. One such undying stereotyping is about the Maasai and other African pastoralists as a people frozen in time (Galaty, 2002; Kratz and Gordon, 2002). Such stereotypes are often built into narratives depicting them as unchanging in order to procure political consensus so as to dispossess them of their commonly held resources, as was the case with the Tanzanian Maasai people (Weldemichel, 2020).

Limitations and recommendations

The study had the following methodological limitations. First, the sample was from workbooks for Grades 1-3, from a government owned publisher. While the findings may provide insight into representation of inclusion in respect of the images analysed in the books from the publisher, the results from this study do not therefore entirely reflect representation of inclusion in books in earlier or later grades nor workbooks from other

publishers. Second, the study was a descriptive quantitative content analysis involving counting frequency of occurrences rather than a semiotic analysis of the images, or what activities characters were involved in the images. Thirdly, in the coding protocol, the signifiers for diversity as proxies for inclusion adopted Kenyan definitions for diversity dimensions such as social class and gender. Gender, for instance, is binary (male or female). Whereas expression or perceptions of gender may vary across societies, the choice of the binary gender view in this study was influenced by the sampled workbooks which presented binary gendered characters.

Representation biases in the learners' workbooks revealed through this study reflect the fact that the authors of the studied workbooks did not sufficiently invest in ensuring that the books do not turn out to be tools for oppression, ethnic hegemony, gender biases, and cultural or religious ideologies. The authors and the authorities in the textbook content production chain need to invest significantly in the process of commissioning and vetting of school textbook authors and publishers.

This study had sampling limitations and was a quantitative content analysis. Further research with much more representative samples of workbooks and a significant number of publishers across the grades could be conducted for a more generalizable study on representation of inclusion. Further research using more in-depth qualitative semiotic or critical discourse analyses may also be used to further study representation of inclusion in the learning workbooks.

Conclusions

This study concludes that in appreciating diversity, the authors and the government authorities involved in the textbook production chain have made significant contribution to advancing inclusive content. By infusing representations of the various diversities, the authors have indeed attempted to promote inclusion of the various groups in the Kenyan society. Whereas those are positive contributions in advancing diversity and inclusion, the weakest point of the content in workbooks is in the reality-distortion and potential for reality-distortion through disproportionate representation or misrepresentation in almost all areas of diversity studied.

References

- AlDahou, N., Ibrahim, H., Park, M., Rahwan, T. and Zaki, Y. (2024). 'Inclusive content reduces racial and gender biases, yet non-inclusive content dominates popular media outlets'. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv-2405.
- Akala, B.M. (2021). 'Revisiting education reform in Kenya: A case of Competency Based Curriculum (CBC)'. *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 3 (1), pp.1-8.
- Baleghizadeh, S. and Shayesteh, L.A. (2020). 'A content analysis of the cultural representations of three ESL grammar textbooks'. *Cogent Education*, 7, pp.1-15.

- Banda, V. (2014). 'The influence of content and structure of Secondary School textbooks on women's careers in the formal sector: Case of selected Schools in Lusaka'. *Association of African Universities Database of African Theses and Dissertation*.
- Briggs, A. and Cobley, P. (eds.). (2002). *The media: an introduction*. Brunswick and London: Pearson Education.
- Cakir, I. (2010). 'The frequency of culture-specific elements in the ELT course books at elementary schools in Turkey'. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on youth and language)*, 4 (2).
- Cameron, D. (1990). *The feminist critique of language: A reader*. London: Routledge.
- Cassimere, R. (2018). 'Fighting for Inclusion: Blacks' Continual Struggle for Citizenship Rights'. *Tricentennial Prosperity Index Collection, The Data Center Research, New Orleans*.
<https://gnocdc.s3.amazonaws.com/reports/TDC-prosperity-brief-raphael-cassimere-FINAL.pdf>
 [Retrieved 26 April 2024].
- Coleman, M. and Glover, D. (2010). *Educational Leadership and Management: Developing Insights and Skills: Developing Insights and Skills*. UK: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Entman, R.M. (1993). 'Framing: towards clarification of a fractured'. *Journal of Communication*, 43 (4), pp.51-58.
- Ferdman, B.M. and Deane, B. (2014). *Diversity at work: The practice of inclusion*. Francisco: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- Galaty, J.G. (2002). 'How Visual Figures Speak: Narrative Inventions of 'The Pastoralist' in East Africa'. *Visual Anthropology*, 15 (3-4), pp.347-367.
- Gharbavi, A. and Mousavi, S.A. (2012). 'A Content Analysis of Textbooks: Investigating Gender Bias as a Social Prominence in Iranian High School English Textbooks'. *English Linguistics Research*, 1 (1), pp.42-49. doi:10.5430/elr.v1n1p42
- Gichuru, F.M., Khayeka-Wandabwa, C., Olkishoo, R., Marinda, P.A., Owaki, M.F., Kathina, M.M. and Yuanyue, W. (2021). 'Education curriculum transitions in Kenya – an account and progress to competency-based education policy'. *Education Curriculum Perspectives*, 4.
- Giles, D. (2003). *Media Psychology*. Routledge.
- Goffman, E. (1974). *Frame analysis: An essay on the organization of experience*. Harvard University Press.
- Gomez-Carrasco, C.J., and Gallego-Herrera, S. (2016). 'The survival of gender stereotypes in the teaching of history. A study through textbooks and the perceptions of secondary school students in Spain'. *Educare* 20 (3). doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.15359/ree.20-3.1
- Government of Kenya. (2010). *Constitution of Kenya*. Nairobi: Government Printers.
- Hall, S. (2003). *Representation: Cultural Representation and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage Publications/The Open University.
- Hamiloglu, K. and Mendi, B. (2010). 'A content analysis related to the cross-cultural/intercultural elements used in EFL course books'. *Sino-US English Teaching*, 7 (1), pp.16-24.
- Harris, R.J. and Sanborn, F.W. (2014). *A cognitive psychology of mass communication* (6th ed.). New York: Routledge.
- Hellinger, M. (1980). 'For men must work, and women must weep': Sexism in English language textbooks used in German schools. *Women's studies international quarterly*, 3 (2) pp.267-75.
- Homan, A.C., Gündemir, S., Buengeler, C. and Van, K. (2020). 'Leading diversity: Towards a theory of functional leadership in diverse teams'. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 105 (10), pp.1-28.
- Jones, B.L., Carter, M.C., Davis, C.M. and Wang, J. (2023). 'Diversity, equity, and inclusion: A decade of progress?' *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice*, 11 (1), pp.116-125.
- Khechen, M. (2013). 'Social justice: Concepts, principles, tools and challenges'. A publication of the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for West Asia; United Nations Economic and Social Council.
- KNBS (2019). *The 2009 Kenya Population and Housing Census*. Nairobi: Kenya National Bureau of Statistics.
- Kolbe, R. and La Voie, J.C. (1981). 'Sex-role stereotyping in preschool children's picture books'. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, pp.369-74.
- Kratz, C.A and Gordon, R. J. (2002). 'Persistent Popular Images of Pastoralists'. *Visual Anthropology*, 15 (3-4), pp.247-265.

- Lesikin, I. (2001). 'Determining social prominence: A methodology for uncovering gender bias in ESL textbooks'. In *Innovation in English Language Teaching*, D.R. Hall and A.Hewing (eds), pp.275-282. London: Routledge.
- Linström, M. and Marais, W. (2012). 'Qualitative News Frame Analysis: A methodology'. *Communitas*, pp.21-38.
- Lumby, J. and Coleman, M. (2007). *Leadership and Diversity: Challenging Theory and Practice in Education*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Machin, D. (2013). 'What is multimodal critical discourse studies?' *Critical Discourse Studies*, 10 (4), pp.347-355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405904.2013.813770>
- Mirza, M. (2004). *Gender analysis of school curriculum and text books*. Islamabad: UNESCO, 2004.
- Moreno-Fernández, O., Moreno-Crespo, P., Pedrero-García, E. and Hunt-Gómez, C.I. (2019). 'Spanish first cycle primary school textbooks' graphic representations. A study on gender, culture and functional diversity'. *Pedagogika/Pedagogy*, 136 (4), pp.67-88.
- Mungwari, T. (2017). *Representation of Political Conflict in the Zimbabwean Press: The Case of the Herald, The Sunday Mail, Daily News and The Standard, 1999-2016*. Pretoria: University of South Africa.
- Mwang'ombe, A.M. (2021). *Competency Based Curriculum (CBC) in Kenya: Teachers understanding and skills, reality on the ground, successes, challenges and recommendations on the implementation of Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in the Kenyan schools*. 10.13140/RG.2.2.35914.49605
- Ndura, E. (2004). 'ESL and Cultural Bias: An analysis of elementary through high school textbooks in the western United States of America'. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 17 (2), pp.143-153.
- Nordin, A. and Sundberg, D. (2018). 'Exploring curriculum change using discursive institutionalism – a conceptual framework'. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 50 (6), pp.820-835.
- Ondimu, S.M. (2018). *Teachers' preparedness for implementation of the competency based curriculum in private pre-schools in Dagoretti North Sub-county, Nairobi City County*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi.
- Owala, J.R. (2021). *Successes and challenges of implementing the competency based curriculum in Kenya*. Institute of Educational Development – East Africa.
- Riffe, D., Lacy, S. and Fico, F. (2014). *Analysing Media Messages: Using quantitative content analysis in research*. New York: Routledge.
- Ramasubramanian, S., Riewestahl, E. and Ramirez, A. (2023). 'Race and Ethnic Stereotypes in the Media'. *Encyclopedia of Race, Ethnicity, and Communication*.
- Tajeddin, Z. and Teimournezhad, S. (2015). 'Exploring the hidden agenda in the representation of culture in international and localised ELT textbooks'. *The Language Learning Journal*, 43 (2), pp.180-193.
- Tikly, L. (2019). 'Education for sustainable development in Africa: A critique of regional agendas'. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 20, pp.223-237.
- Tuchman, G. (1978). *Making news: A study in the construction of reality*. New York: Free Press.
- Tukachinsky, R. (2017). 'Media portrayals and effects: African Americans'. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Communication*.
- Ullah, H. and Skelton, C. (2013). 'Gender representation in the public sector school's textbooks of Pakistan'. *Educational Studies*. 39 (2), pp.183-94.
- Weldemichel, T.G. (2020). 'Othering pastoralists, state violence, and the remaking of boundaries in Tanzania's militarised wildlife conservation sector'. *Antipode*, 52 (5), pp.1496-1518.
- Weninger, C. and Kiss, T. (2013). 'Culture in English as a foreign language (EFL) textbooks: A semiotic approach'. *TESOL Quarterly*, 47 (4), pp.694-716.
- Wolbrecht, C. and Hero, R.E. (2005). *Politics of Democratic Inclusion*. Temple University Press.
- Zeenatunissa, M. (1989). 'Sex discrimination in education: Content analysis of Pakistan school text books'. *ISS Working Paper Series/General Series*, 62, pp.1-61.

Samuel Kochomay is a Journalism and Mass Communication lecturer at Mount Kenya University, Kenya. His research interests cover communication and development, media representations of conflict, peace and development, sports for peace and development. He has published the following papers and book chapters: 'A Comparative Analysis of Age-Set and Generation Sets in East Africa: Lesson for the Teaching of History in Tanzania'; 'Dialectics of war and peace: Pokot alternate regimes of war and peace'; 'Communicating peace through sports'[book chapter]; 'Traditional African Culture and Communication: The Missing Link in Cattle Rustling Interventions among Pastoralist Communities in Northern Kenya'[book chapter]; 'Sport for Peace: Opportunities and challenges'[book chapter].

kochomay@consultant.com; skochomay@mku.ac.ke.